

Relative Efficiency of Anions in Releasing Phosphate from Acid Soils

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Of the eight anions F⁻, Cl⁻, B⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, S²⁻, S₂O₃²⁻ and SO₄²⁻ studied, F⁻ is most effective in releasing phosphate from acid soils and SO₄²⁻, the least. The order of efficiency of these anions in P-release is F⁻ > S²⁻ > S₂O₃²⁻ > I⁻ > NO₃⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻ > SO₄²⁻.

NATIVE and applied phosphates in acid soils can be mobilized to some extent by the application of inorganic salt solutions. Cameron and Hurst¹ observed that neutral salts in general depress the solubility of AlPO₄ and KCl and NaNO₃ depress the solubility of iron phosphate. Hibbard² however observed that neutral salt solutions containing monovalent cation such as KCl, NH₄Cl, NH₄NO₃ and Na₂SO₄ extract about the same amount of soil phosphate as does distilled water, the effect of F⁻ in phosphate release from acid soils studied by various workers (Swenson *et al.*³; Turner and Rice⁴; Chang and Jackson²) Kar⁵ observed that increase in calcium status gradually released soil phosphorus. The maximum release of phosphorus is noted with Ca(OH)₂ and is significantly higher than KOH and Ca(NO₃)₂. Gupta⁶ observed that lime in combination with nitrogen as ammonium sulfate in general depressed the availability of P₂O₅ in the soil. Prabhakar *et al.*⁷ observed that addition of both (NH₄)₂SO₄ and KNO₃ increased the available phosphorus content in red sandy loam soil (pH 6.7) but the effect of (NH₄)₂SO₄ was less as compared with KNO₃.

Experimental

In the present experiment three acid soils, two from West Bengal, viz., Kaksa (Burdwan), Mohammed Bazar (Birbhum) and one from Bhutan (Thimpo) were used. The characterisation of the soil is described in Table 1.

2 gms of each of soil sample of Kaksa (K), Mohammed Bazar (M) and Thimpo (T) was taken with 0.2 gm of the reagent in different stoppered bottles with 50 ml distilled water and kept for 3 months with occasional shaking. A few drops of toluene were added to check fungal growth. The reagents used were different salts of a particular cation i.e., Na⁺ with different anions, in case of S²⁻ alone CaS was used; pH being adjusted to 6.5 initially. After the desired period, the phosphate release was determined colorimetrically by the vanadomolybdate method (Jackson⁵).

The results are shown in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that anions are effective with a wide range from 8.0 to 87.7% in releasing phosphate from acid soils. Fluoride ion F⁻ is the most effective anion in such release and it releases phosphate about 86.5% from the soil, 87.7% from T-soil and 83.6% from M-soil. Next to F⁻ ion is sulfide ion, S²⁻ this being probably due to the gradual precipitation of ferrous sulfide through the reactions:

The release of phosphate by calcium sulfide is 29.7% for K-soil, 26.7% for T-soil and 27.3% for M-soil.

TABLE 1—SOME PARTICULARS OF THE SOILS

Locality	Latitude and Longitude of place	family	pH	Organic C %	C.E.C. me/100 gms	% of HCl soluble		
						Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	P ₂ O ₅
Kaksa (K)	23°28' N + 87°26' E	Lateritic	4.80	0.43	5.25	4.45	5.05	0.084
Mohammed Bazar (M)	24°2' N + 87°2' E	,,	6.15	0.52	10.35	3.05	4.35	0.076
Thimpo (T)	27°30' N + 89°30' E	Hilly forest	5.80	1.72	11.45	3.80	4.65	0.130

TABLE 2—RELEASE OF PHOSPHATE BY DIFFERENT ANIONS

Soil sample	Treatment with	pH			Release of P in $g \times 10^{-3}$ per gm soil	% of P-release to total phosphorus content
		initial	adjusted	Final		
I. K-soil	1. Water (control)	4.80	6.5	6.10	0.020	5.4
	2. NaF	6.20	6.5	5.65	0.320	86.5
	3. NaCl	4.15	6.5	6.10	0.040	10.8
	4. NaBr	4.25	6.5	6.15	0.043	11.6
	5. NaI	4.05	6.5	6.05	0.046	12.5
	6. NaNO ₃	4.40	6.5	6.00	0.045	12.2
	7. Na ₂ SO ₄	4.50	6.5	6.35	0.030	8.1
	8. Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	4.65	6.5	5.95	0.065	17.6
	9. CaS	7.15	6.5	5.85	0.110	29.7
II. T-soil	1. Water (control)	5.80	6.5	6.05	0.033	5.8
	2. NaF	6.15	6.5	5.30	0.500	87.7
	3. NaCl	5.30	6.5	5.90	0.057	10.0
	4. NaBr	5.50	6.5	5.85	0.058	10.2
	5. NaI	5.30	6.5	5.75	0.062	10.9
	6. NaNO ₃	5.15	6.5	5.65	0.060	10.5
	7. Na ₂ SO ₄	5.60	6.5	6.00	0.045	8.0
	8. Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	5.85	6.5	5.80	0.080	14.0
	9. CaS	7.10	6.5	5.70	0.150	26.7
III. M-soil	1. Water (control)	6.15	6.5	6.50	0.015	5.3
	2. NaF	6.35	6.5	5.50	0.280	83.6
	3. NaCl	5.50	6.5	6.00	0.031	9.7
	4. NaBr	5.70	6.5	5.95	0.033	10.0
	5. NaI	5.50	6.5	5.90	0.036	10.9
	6. NaNO ₃	5.15	6.5	5.85	0.035	10.6
	7. Na ₂ SO ₄	5.70	6.5	6.00	0.020	6.1
	8. Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	6.00	6.5	5.80	0.075	20.3
	9. CaS	7.30	6.5	5.70	0.090	27.3

The higher phosphate release by F⁻, obviously due to complex formation reaction and in the case of S²⁻ is due to reduction of FePO₄ to FeS.

The slight higher release of phosphate by thio-sulfate ion, S₂O₃²⁻ than other anions e.g., Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, I⁻ etc. is probably due to its weak reducing properties and complex formation reaction. The higher release of phosphorus by NO₃⁻ than SO₄²⁻ is probably due to its higher solubility and sorption properties.

The phosphate release property by different anions from K, T and M soils follow the order :

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